

DTws dimension aggregation development

- DTwA user
- Domain expert

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- DTwA user

DTws metadata
instantiation

DTwA Entity Creation

DTwA Digital Entity
Aggregation

DTwA Connections
Creation

DTwA Entity +
Instantiation

DTwA Digital Entity +
Instantiation

DTwA Connections +
Instantiation